

**MASTERS' PROFESSIONAL TRAINING ON SPECIALTY
016.02 «SPECIAL EDUCATION. OLIGOFRENOPELAGOGY»
IN H.S.SKOVORODA KHARKIV NATIONAL
PEDAGOGICAL UNIVERSITY**

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Trends in the labor market are evidenced by the lack of special education teachers and correctional education teachers in Ukraine. In order to realize this task, the modern Ukrainian school needs specialists capable of professional activity in the field of education, upbringing and development of children with special educational needs.

The precondition for the Oligophrenopedagogy educational programme working out is the fact that in Ukraine the number of children with special educational needs is rapidly increasing, in particular with intellectual, behavioral disorders, disorders of the emotional and volitional sphere, ASD, complex disorders and others. Therefore, Oligophrenopedagogy is a response to society's challenges in training professionals to work with children with SEN.

The educational program "Oligophrenopedagogy" was created in accordance with the Laws of Ukraine "On Education", "On Higher Education" and the

regulations of the Cabinet of Ministers “On Approval of the National Framework of Qualifications”, “Approval of the National Qualifications Framework”, “On Approval of the License Terms for Educational Activities”.

Different problems of special education teachers’ professional training were studied by P.Edelen-Smith, M.Prater, T.Sileo [1], C.Forlin, K.Tait, A.Carroll, A.Jobling, [2], F.Reed, L. Monda-Amaya [3], S.Trent, E.Pernell, A.Mungai, R.Chimedza [4], R.Villa, J.Thousand, J.Chapple [5], J.G.Wishart, G.Manning [6] and others.

The content of the educational programme provides for the formation of applicants’ knowledge, skills and abilities to work with children with intellectual disabilities through the use of the latest innovative and health-preserving technologies.

The educational programme (EP) was introduced in the educational process in 2020. The volume of EP is 90 ECTS credits / 1 year 4 months. EP takes into account a comprehensive system of integrated learning, built on innovative project results, taking into account the problems of modern special education and inclusive education of children with intellectual disabilities, the most pressing problems of modern correctional psychopedagogy, pedagogy.

The results of the survey “Assessment of cooperation with employers” show that 100% of employers said they were ready to accept applicants for internships, 75% confirmed their willingness to cooperate with the university on the model of dual education, and 62.5% said they could to accept teachers for internships. 87.5% of respondents are willing to cooperate with the university in order to improve educational training programs.

Practical training of masters involves passing pedagogical practice in institutions of special education and research practice.

Improving educational and methodological and informational support of EP disciplines, more active involvement of applicants in research work, participation in conferences of various levels will help to improve training on the EP. It is planned to expand cooperation with inclusive resource centers, special schools, general

secondary education institutions with inclusive education of children with intellectual disabilities in the Kharkiv region, through consultative meetings, round tables and other joint activities.

High school teachers who provide training for students at the EP have sufficient scientific, educational and practical experience of teaching at the profile departments of H.S.Skovoroda KhNPU.

Before passing each of the internships, the masters attend the mentoring conferences, during the internship its head from the educational institution provides consultations to the applicants and directly supervises its process. Leading methods of teaching are: productive-practical, partial-search, executive ones. The final assessment of the internship is carried out according to the national system of differential credit and the system of ECTS assessments. Attestation of graduates of the educational program of specialty 016 Special education is carried out in the form of defense of qualification work.

Thus, we can make a conclusion that the EP “Oligophrenopedagogy” which is provided for masters’ professional training on specialty 016.02 «Special education. Oligofrenopedagogy» in H.S.Skovoroda Kharkiv national pedagogical university makes their fundamental training for future teaching in the system of special and inclusive education.

References

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